

GERMPLASM CONSERVATION AND EVALUATION OF JACKFRUIT (*Artocarpus heterophyllus*) UNDER PERIYAKULAM CONDITIONS

HGRP
63

Dr C.Subesh Ranjith Kumar, Dr.J.Rajangam, Dr.V.Premlakshmi and Dr.C.Sankar
Department of Fruit Science, Hort. College & Res.Institute, Periyakulam
Tamil Nadu Agricultural University

Abstract

- 27 Jack fruit accessions were evaluated for vegetative, flowering and fruiting characters.
- Accessions AH2, AH 18 and AH 15 were found to be promising for different commercial traits.
- Palur 1 was taken up as standard check.

Objectives

- To survey the jackfruit growing regions and record the variability in relation to growth, flowering, fruiting and quality as per the IPGRI / NBPGR descriptor.
- To identify the promising accessions for off season types, small fruit with less than 5 kg, high TSS, less latex, red carpel and high yield

Acknowledgment

ICAR
AICRP (FRUITS)
&
TNAU

Introduction

- The Jack fruit tree (*Artocarpus heterophyllus*) belonging to the family Moraceae is considered to be indigenous to the rain forest of Western ghats of India
- High variability and diversity favours new choice of accessions to market demand
- Exploration, Conservation, evaluation in the form of ex situ conservation been taken up as an experiment at Dept. of Fruit Science, TNAU, Periyakulam under ICAR AICRP (Fruits)

Materials and Methods

- Treatment Design: : RBD
- No. of plants per replication : 4
- Number of plants/treatment : 4
- Spacing : 7 x 7 m
- Start of experiment : Since 2012
- 40 kg of FYM + 600:320:400g of N: P₂O₅: K₂O as Urea, Super phosphate and Muriate of potash
- Drip irrigation
- PoP as per Crop Production guide of TNAU
- Observations to be recorded on growth and fruit characters both on and off season

GERMPLASM COLLECTION – FIELD VIEW

References

- Akter,A (2017). Evaluation of Jack fruit (*Artocarpus heterophyllus* Lam.) Germplasm. Research & Reviews: Journal of Botany ISSN: 2278-2222 (Online) Volume 7, Issue 1 pp. 38-53
- Mitra SK, Maity CS. Genetic resources of Jackfruit (*Artocarpus heterophyllus*) in West Bengal, India. Acta Hort. 2000; 575: 269–71p

Result and Discussion

GROWTH & YIELD CHARACTERS

Acc. No	Tree height (m)	No. of Fruits
AH-1	7.90	10
AH-2	7.32	32
AH-4	7.30	8
AH-5	7.18	6
AH-6	7.30	11
AH-7	6.48	12
AH-8	5.02	2
AH-10	4.86	5
AH-11	4.92	7
AH-13	5.40	2
AH-15	6.34	15
AH-16	5.80	2
AH-17	7.40	3
AH-18	6.38	26

Promising accession – AH 2

Conclusion

- AH2 has recorded the highest number of fruits (32) and bearing off season nature followed by AH 18 (26 fruits)
- AH2 possessed less latex and high TSS (24⁰ B) when compared with standard check Palur 1 (18⁰ B)
- AH 15 another promising accession with big sized fruit with 310 flakes, weighing 23.50 kg and with high TSS of 26⁰B in comparison with Palur 1 (12.50 kg).